

Description of a 16-channel gas manifold.

Purpose and use of the device

The manifold allows control of 16 gas channels by opening solenoid valves (SV) and by letting gas flow to another compartment. It was designed to create 16 closed loops on which gas analysers are plugged. However it may be used for another purpose such as gas mixing, or in a mode with open loops.

Figure 1: Schematic view of the manifold. The two racks of SV are represented by the blue (1 IN to 16 OUT) and the green (16 IN and 1 OUT) circuits. The dashed lines represent the tubes that are necessary in order to create closed loops, for gas analysis for instance.

Description

The manifold is composed of the following main components (fig. 1):

- **32 Solenoid valves (DCX 321 - MATRIX).** They are either open or closed, and let the gas through or not. They are assembled in 2 racks of 16. The first rack (GM 320.053 – BIBUS) has one inlet and 16 outlets. It aims at distributing the gas into 16 compartments. The second rack (GM 320.054 – BIBUS) has 16 inlets and 1 outlet. It collects gas from different compartments and directs it to a common line. The 2 racks are assembled on a veroboard (fig. 2 and 3). The SV are controlled in pairs (the corresponding one of each rack, fig.1). For this, the positive terminals of the paired SV are brazed together on the veroboard. The supply voltage is 24 volts.
- **An Ethernet relay (ETH8020-B),** eventually with its protective case (ETH8020-C). It contains 20 changeover relays that can be controlled via the Ethernet port. One relay is attributed to a pair of SV. It is possible to use the remaining relays to operate an indicator

light, for instance. The control of the relay is achievable via a web-based interface by manually choosing the relay to open, or via a program.

- **Tubes (PARKER/LEGRIS).** The tubes direct the gas in and out of the manifold. The single connector (IN or OUT) of the SV rack accept 4*6 mm tubes (inner and outer diameter respectively), whereas the 16 small connectors accept 2.5*4 mm tubes (fig. 2 and 3). We recommend installing filters to protect the SV.
- **Optional: gas analysers and a pumping system.** The manifold was designed to create several loops of gas analysis. For this purpose, we connected gas analysers in series downstream of the GM.320.054 rack. For the gas to flow, it is also necessary to insert a pumping system. In our case, we used a pump that was integrated into the analyser.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the 2 racks of SV, assembled on a veroboard. The left yellow connector is for connection to the Ethernet relay and the right one is for the power supply (24 V).

Figure 3: Photography of a SV rack assembled on a veroboard. The apparent wires connect the SV to the pins of the connector (the paired SV of the rack below the veroboard is connected to the same pin) to establish communication with the Ethernet relay.

Application example

We used this manifold to measure CO_2 and O_2 in the pores of a substrate that was contained in mesocosms (72 cm-high HDPE columns). The substrate was ground basalt, on which we cultivated *Medicago sativa*. With this design, we aimed at measuring CO_2 and O_2 exchanges due to the plants' activity. Between the outlet of the rack GM 320.054 and the inlet of the rack GM 320.053, we had a closed single line, on which we plugged a CO_2 analyser containing a pump and a T-shaped connector that contained an optical sensor connected to an O_2 analyser (fig. 4). On the other side of the manifold, we had 16 closed loops passing through the mesocosms thanks to cable glands. In our example, we performed an analysis in 5 mesocosms, at 3 different depths. Inside the mesocosm, a gas-permeable membrane (MEMBRANA-ACCUREL) allows the air to enter the loop. With this system, the air is returned to the mesocosm. In order to avoid the mixing of the gas between different compartments, we used one channel of the manifold to flush the system: Instead of passing through a mesocosm, the 16th loop of tubes passed through a sealed box containing soda lime in order to capture CO_2 . Compared to ambient air, this ensures that changes in channels were detected, especially for CO_2 , even for low CO_2 concentrations in the mesocosms. It also prevents too much variation in the flush, which would otherwise be dependent on the surroundings and therefore on the biotic daily variations or on human interventions. A flush was performed between each measuring slot.

In the CSV file “CO2_measure_example”, attached to this document, we report the raw CO_2 concentrations for one month of measurement in one mesocosm (3 depths).

Figure 4: Schematic view of the manifold used for CO₂ and O₂ analysis in mesocosms. Inside the mesocosms, a gas-permeable membrane is in place. 'Upstream' and 'Downstream' annotations are relative to the mesocosm.

Data post-processing

The frequency of the data is dependent on the analyser or on the data acquisition process. The measuring time per channel is defined by the user. In the case of an application similar to the example, we recommend waiting long enough for the system to be at equilibrium. Indeed, there is a lag dependent on the length and volume of the pipes conducting the gas, and on the difference in concentration with the previous channel. For instance, as we used soda lime for the flush in our example, the first measures of the next channel are low and not representative of the medium we want to analyse. In our case, we had chosen a 4-minute measuring time for each channel, which gave us 9 to 10 data points with our system. This duration was sufficient to reach a plateau for CO₂ values below 3000 ppm, whereas a longer measuring time might be needed for higher concentrations (fig. 5). In such a case, we recommend adapting the measuring time to the system, and to retain only the last value of the time slot.

Fig. 6 shows a CO₂ plot before and after post-processing.

Figure 5: Raw CO₂ data before post-process. Pore CO₂ concentrations for 3 different depths of the mesocosm and for the flush channel. Each color refer to channel. Each measuring timeslot is 4-minutes long.

Figure 6: Two CO₂ plots recorded in the basalt of one mesocosm at 3 depths before (upper panel) and after post-processing (lower panel). The large drop in concentration is due to a heavy irrigation that led to CO₂ dissolution in water.

Limitations

In the example, we see that the first two measurements (out of the 9 or 10) of a measuring slot are greatly affected by the previous channel (fig. 5). For instance, we observe a very low CO₂ value after a flush. This means that a pollution of the compartment by the air of the previous one is to consider, due to the remaining air in the tubes. However, it can be reduced by lowering the volumes contained in the tubes.

Monitoring the pressure and the temperature inside the tubes of the manifold might be challenging. This might have an impact if the gas analysis requires these parameters as inputs to calculate a concentration from the raw values it collected. To limit this bias, we propose to calibrate the analyser by using the manifold.

Acknowledgements

Didier Jehanno led the development of the hardware and carried out the electronics assembly. Simon Chollet created the code to run the manifold in the example.